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D6.3 - Data Management Plan Update

Project Acronym:	MOBILES
Project Title:	Monitoring and Detection of Biotic and Abiotic Pollutants by Electronic Plants and Microorganisms Based Sensors
Grant Agreement:	101135402
Project coordinator:	prof. Evangelos Hristoforou dr. Angelo Ferraro National Technical University of Athens (NTUA)
Call:	HORIZON-CL6-2023-ZEROPOLLUTION-01.
Topic:	HORIZON-CL6-2023-ZEROPOLLUTION-01-6
Type of action:	HORIZON Research and Innovation Actions
Granting Authority:	European Research Executive Agency

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Deliverable D6.3 - Data Management Plan update Update

Short summary:	This deliverable is the update of the first version of the Data Management Plan (DMP) for the MOBILES project, funded under Horizon Europe. It outlines the management of 22 datasets and 21 public deliverables following FAIR principles and EU Open Science policy. The DMP ensures data findability, accessibility, interoperability, and reusability, using trusted repositories (Zenodo). Sensitive datasets are protected for commercial exploitation, while open-access outputs are licensed under Creative Commons. This document serves as a living platform for continuous updates throughout the project's lifecycle.
Due date:	30/04/2026
WP, leader:	WP 6, NTUA
Authors:	Linda Šulc Dalecká, GG

Dissemination Level

PU Public	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
SEN Sensitive	<input type="checkbox"/>

Document history

Version	Date	Name	Chapters edited	Reason for change
V1	23/04/2026	Linda Šulc Dalecká	All	Document prepared
V1.1	27/04/2026	Angelo Ferraro	All	Document reviewed
V2.0	29/04/2026	Linda Šulc Dalecká	All	Document reviewed
V3.0	29/04/2026	Angelo Ferraro	All	Document approved

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List of participants

Participant No	Participant organisation name	Country
1 Coordinator	ETHNICON METSOVION POLYTECHNION (NTUA)	GR
2	CONSIGLIO NAZIONALE DELLE RICERCHE (CNR)	IT
3	INSTITUT NATIONAL DE RECHERCHE POUR L'AGRICULTURE, L'ALIMENTATION ET L'ENVIRONNEMENT (INRAE)	FR
4	UNIVERSITA DEGLI STUDI DI ROMA LA SAPIENZA (UR)	IT
5	EDEN TECH (EDEN)	FR
6	UNIVERSIDAD PUBLICA DE NAVARRA (UPNA)	ES
7	INSTYTUT UPRAWY NAWOZENIA I GLEBOZNAWSTWA, PANSTWOWY INSTYTUT BADAWCZY (ISSPC)	PL
8	THE AGRICULTURAL RESEARCH ORGANISATION OF ISRAEL - THE VOLCANI CENTRE (ARO)	IL
9	UNIVERSITE DE BORDEAUX (UBx)	FR
10	TECNOLOGIKO PANEPISTIMIO KYPROU (CUT)	CY
11	HEMIJSKI FAKULTET, UNIVERZITET U BEOGRADU (UBE)	RS
12	MAT4NRG-GESELLSCHAFT FUR MATERIALIEN UND ENERGIEANWENDUNGEN MBH (Mat)	DE
13	TECHNISCHE UNIVERSITAT CLAUSTHAL (TUC)	DE
14	GRANT GARANT SRO (GG)	CZ
15	CENTRUM BADAN I INNOWACJI PRO-AKADEMIA STOWARZYSZENIE (RICPA)	PL

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1. SUMMARY

The MOBILES project, funded under the Horizon Europe programme, aims to develop portable, cost-effective, and high-performing biosensors for the detection and mitigation of environmental pollutants, including pathogens, Chemicals of Emerging Concern (CECs), and Persistent Mobile Chemicals (PMCs). The project focuses on improving air, soil, and water quality through innovative technologies that benefit human and environmental health. It includes the following objectives:

- **Objective 1: Development of Electronic Biosensors:** For monitoring organic chemicals (e.g., pesticides, hormones) and antimicrobial-resistant bacteria/pathogens in air, water, and soil.
- **Objective 2: Development of Organism-Based Biosensors:** Using genetically modified organisms (e.g., chemiluminescent bacteria, colour-changing plants, and marine diatoms) for detecting organic/inorganic pollutants and monitoring bioplastic degradation in aquatic environments.
- **Objective 3: Environmental Performance Studies:** Assessing the ecological impact of developed biosensors and devices.
- **Objective 4: Metagenomics Analysis:** Investigating microbiota in polluted areas to identify functional gene clusters.
- **Objective 5: Safety Tests:** Conducting EFSA-like assessments to evaluate environmental safety.

The project outputs, including biosensors and monitoring systems, will cater to a broad range of stakeholders, from consumers to industry operators and emergency responders, ensuring adaptability to various pollutants.

MOBILES Data Management Plan (DMP)

The MOBILES Data Management Plan (DMP), a deliverable of Work Package 6 (WP6) delivered by task T6.4 leader, GRANT Garant (GG) ensures responsible management of all research data and outputs in compliance with the FAIR principles (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable) and Open Access (OA) policy.

Key aspects of this deliverable include:

- **Definition of Datasets Generated:** The project will produce 22 datasets and 21 other research outputs (public deliverables) across its six work packages.
- **Findability:** Open datasets will be deposited primarily in Zenodo (under MOBILES community: <https://zenodo.org/communities/mobiles>), using persistent identifiers (e.g., DOIs) and Creative Commons licensing (CC BY for data, CC0 for metadata). Restricted datasets will follow stringent confidentiality measures.
- **Accessibility:** Majority of project datasets and other research outputs will have granted open access. Some project datasets and other research outputs (sensitive deliverables) will not be open in order to protect know-how for potential patent application.

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- **Interoperability:** Common open formats (e.g., MS Office, CSV, FASTA, PDF) will ensure compatibility with widely available tools, while proprietary formats will be supported by licensed software or Python libraries.
- **Reusability:** Comprehensive metadata, README files, and descriptive documentation will accompany datasets, ensuring ease of access, reproducibility, and compliance with Horizon Europe requirements.
- **Updates:** This Deliverable is a first update of DMP prepared in M4 and will be further updated in M40. D6.3 provides a dynamic framework for ongoing improvements.

The MOBILES project is committed to transparency and open science principles while balancing ethical, legal, and commercial considerations.

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2. MOBILES Project short description

The National Technical University of Athens (NTUA) is working with another 15 partners from academia, research, and industry to develop prototypes of electronic and organism-based biosensors to monitor organic chemicals, antimicrobial-resistant (AMR) bacteria, and pathogens in water, soil, and air.

The MOBILES project is studying and developing biosensors for detecting heavy metals, antibiotics, pesticides, arsenic, microplastics, and nanoplastics. It is also developing genetically modified plants and bacteria for detecting heavy metals, antibiotics, and pesticides, and the use of marine diatoms for monitoring bioplastic degradation.

MOBILES aims are to tackle chemicals, including persistent and mobile (PMCs) pollutants and contaminants of emerging concern (CECs), that degrade the environment. Another severe global health risk is associated with increasing AMR in bacteria. Foodborne pathogens, including *Listeria*, *Salmonella*, and *Campylobacter*, pose significant public health risks and are already monitored. However, current bacterial detection methods for environmental control are slow and require specialized laboratories with trained personnel. Similarly, conventional pollutant detection methods, such as chromatography and mass spectrometry, are accurate but time-consuming and require specialized equipment. State-of-the-art detection methods are unsuitable for constant on-site and real-time monitoring. The long time between sampling and detection reduces the efficiency of public health and environmental protection authorities in implementing effective countermeasures. To tackle this problem, several electrochemical biosensors will be developed within the MOBILES project.

Biosensors are devices that combine biological elements with electronic systems to detect specific pollutants. The MOBILES project enhances these sensors with advanced nanomaterials, significantly improving their sensitivity and reliability. All biosensors will have common basic electronics and functional principles (e.g., an organic ligand able to recognize target pollutants), but they will differ in the biological element employed: (i) aptasensors based on aptamers that recognize bacterial cells or spore surfaces, (ii) electronic noses for detecting and quantifying volatile organic compounds (VOCs) produced by bacteria, (iii) genosensors for detecting genes involved in antibiotic resistance, and (iv) interdigital capacitors functionalized with aptamers for 17 β -estradiol, a member of CECs family.

Continual threats (such as industrial pollution and the overuse of drugs and pesticides) to sources of drinking water require real-time solutions for wide-ranging water monitoring systems to detect toxicants such as heavy metals, pesticides, and antibiotics. Conventional methods are limited in their ability to detect sub-lethal concentrations of active antibacterial compounds. The damage caused by the activity of an antibacterial agent or pesticide may stimulate different biological mechanisms of bacterial repair. Each antibiotic and/or pesticide triggers specific cellular pathways, mechanisms, and targets within the bacterial cell. This specific biological response, enabling the detection of antibiotics and pesticides using microorganisms, is being investigated in the MOBILES project through the use of genetically modified bacteria to detect toxic pollutants in water. For detecting heavy metals (cadmium, chromium, lead, mercury) in water, MOBILES is developing a flow-through

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device for continuous monitoring using biological systems (genetically modified bacteria) combined with an optical sensor and flow unit.

Highly toxic arsenic pollution can come from various sources, including industrial activities, mining, and even natural processes. Water and food contaminated by arsenic can cause serious health problems, including cancer and heart disease. For detecting arsenic pollution in soil and groundwater, the MOBILES project is developing genetically modified plants that change colour when arsenic is present in the soil or water used to grow them. The project will conduct safety evaluations to ensure that the genetically modified organisms and developed devices have minimal environmental impact. A specific work package (WP4) is dedicated to evaluate the effects of genetically modified organisms on other organisms and the environment. Safety tests and environmental impact of MOBILES organisms are performed in laboratory using EFSA guidelines.

Microplastic and nanoplastic pollution is raising concerns about its potential impact on human health. The transfer of very small plastics through the trophic chain is a potential source of contamination at all trophic levels. Understanding the distribution, degradation, and life cycle of micro- and nanoplastics in the marine environment is limited by the intrinsic difficulties of current techniques for detecting, quantifying, and chemically identifying small particles in liquids. The MOBILES project is addressing this challenge by utilizing marine diatoms. Diatoms are known for their resilience and adaptability, making them ideal candidates for studying the biodegradation of bioplastics in marine environments. Preliminary studies have shown promising results, indicating that diatoms not only survive in environments containing bioplastics but also contribute to their biodegradation.

In addition to the development of sensors, MOBILES will undertake comprehensive metagenomic analysis, profiling the microbiota of polluted areas across Europe. This work will uncover gene clusters and reveal genetic diversity, enabling a deeper understanding of microbial functions. These insights will provide genetic markers to facilitate rapid evaluation of soil and land health. Two annual sampling rounds are planned for at least two years, and sample collection will be conducted at different locations to target microbiota related to specific pollution types: Greece for urban wastewater contamination, Poland for heavy metal pollution, Cyprus for microplastics and plastics, France for agriculture and animal farming, Italy for arsenic, and Germany for chemicals and heavy metals from former mining activities. Genomic and transcriptomic data will be analysed, visualized, and interpreted using bioinformatic tools and soil metagenomic web-based platform specifically realized by MOBILES partners. The project's data storage, located in Spain, will be connected to other well-known genomic databases in order to provide a wide range of information.

The biosensors will be rigorously tested with real-world samples from polluted sites to validate their environmental performance.

MOBILES workplan is organized in 6 WPs listed in Table 1. Management actions and collaboration with other EU funded projects are implemented within WP6 while disseminations, exploitation and communication (DEC) activities are grouped within WP5. WP1-WP2 deal with interconnected scientific and technological activities to develop electrochemical biosensors to detect specific pollutants, and organism-based biosensor to monitor other typology of selected pollutants. In WP3

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an extensive metagenomic analysis will be performed in order to enable searches for diverse functionalities across multiple gene clusters in polluted and not polluted areas across Europe. In WP4 the safety of all genetically modified bacteria and plants will be tested using standard EU procedures (e.g., EFSA guidelines for genetically modified organisms), and a pre-industrial design of the various biosensors will be provided along with stability (shelf-life) tests.

Table 1. MOBILES WPs list

WP	Work Package Title	Lead Name	Start Month	End month
1	Electronic biosensors for environmental monitoring	INRAE	1	36
2	Detection of pollutants via biotic sensors	UR	1	36
3	Metagenomics database and fully-sequenced polluted soil microbiota	CNR- ISAFOM	1	42
4	Environmental performance and safety of developed organisms, and packaging of sensor devices	RICPA	10	42
5	Dissemination, exploitation and communication of project outcomes	GG	1	42
6	Project Management and Coordination	NTUA	1	42

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3. MOBILES Data Summary

3.1. PRINCIPLES OF THE DATA MANAGEMENT

MOBILES is a Research and Innovation Action project funded under the Horizon Europe programme. Over its 42-month long duration, the project will generate multiple digital datasets from various consortium members. Developing a viable Data Management Plan (DMP) to guide the team through the processes of data storage, availability, accessibility, and reuse, in compliance with the FAIR principles, represents a critical first step in the project's realization.

The guiding principles of the EU Open Science policy, broadly outlined in Annex V of the EU Grants Annotated Grant Agreement, along with the indicative DMP template, have provided a framework for creating a comprehensive plan to effectively manage data within the MOBILES project.

The Data Management Plan of the MOBILES project aims to:

- Deliver and regularly update a comprehensive **DMP, with scheduled updates at M20 and M40** of the project timeline.
- Manage all data in accordance with **FAIR principles** to ensure findability, accessibility, interoperability, and reusability.
- Deposit data in a **trusted repository (Zenodo)** as soon as possible in case of scientific publications, upon publication.
- Ensure open access to research data through the repository, using the latest version of the **Creative Commons Attribution International Public License (CC BY)** or the **Creative Commons Public Domain Dedication (CC0)**. Exceptions will be made if openness harms the beneficiaries' legitimate interests or contradicts constraints such as EU competitive interests or obligations under the Grant Agreement (note Art. 17).
- Provide repository-based information about research outputs and any tools or instruments required to reuse or validate the data.
- Ensure open **metadata (licensed under CC0)**, including key details such as the dataset's origin, publication information (author(s), title, date of publication, and venue), Horizon Europe grant information (project name, acronym, and number), licensing terms, and persistent identifiers for the publication, authors, organizations, and the grant. Where applicable, metadata will also include persistent identifiers for any research outputs or tools required to validate the publication's conclusions.

3.2. OBJECTIVES OF THE DATA MANAGEMENT PLAN

The current deliverable, D6.3, represents the updated version of the MOBILES project's Data Management Plan (DMP) submitted at M4. This plan supports the project team in achieving the efficient implementation of research objectives in compliance with the Grant Agreement and Open Science policy. Additionally, it facilitates effective communication, dissemination of project results, and project reporting.

The current MOBILES DMP update has been developed as part of Work Package 6 (WP6), Task 6.4, whose main objectives are to:

- **Identify the main research digital datasets** that will be produced and link each dataset to the relevant project objective.
- **Ensure data management practices** adhere to the FAIR principles and promote Open Access/Open Data sharing.
- **Define key details for each dataset**, including formats, storage methods, restrictions for sensitive datasets (e.g., denial of access rights), and relevant repositories for storage.
- **Provide a dynamic platform** for ongoing updates and enhancements to Data Management practices.

The MOBILES DMP addresses both the digital research data generated within the project and other research outputs (notably, public deliverables). It is based on dataset information collected through an internal survey of MOBILES consortium members conducted during M3–M4 of the project. The survey was repeated again during M20 and small changes have been added to the current version. This document will be updated and expanded as necessary in M40.

3.3. DATA MANAGEMENT IN THE MOBILES PROJECT

Data management is a key task within WP6 (Project Management and Coordination), which is led by NTUA, the project coordinator. Within WP6, Task 6.4, focused on data management, is led by GG. The DMP form was prepared in coordination with the project coordinator and in close collaboration with all project team members, following a DMP template provided by EU authorities (EU Funding & Tender Portal-Reference Documents). This effort aimed to establish a solid foundation for the project's DMP, including its principles and objectives.

In addition, GG provides guidance to the entire project team throughout the data lifecycle and ensures they are informed about their relevant data management obligations. GG is also responsible for conducting periodic reviews of the DMP, working collaboratively with all project team members.

All related questionnaires are securely stored internally on the project's Google Drive.

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3.4. SUMMARY OF MOBILES DATA AND OTHER RESEARCH OUTPUTS

The MOBILES project is structured into 6 work packages, 4 of which are dedicated to research and innovation. WP5 focuses on the dissemination, exploitation, and communication of project outcomes, while WP6 is responsible for project management and coordination.

The MOBILES project has identified 22 broad datasets that are generating and will generate data over its course. A brief description of these datasets, including their origin, format, and relation to the project's objectives, is provided in Table 2 (*See Attachments*).

Additionally, the project will produce approximately 21 other research outputs, primarily public deliverables provided in Table 2 (*See Attachments*).

Compared to the previous DMP version, two datasets (DAT_02b_CNR-ISAFOM and DAT_06_UPNA) have been consolidated into a single dataset (DAT_02b_WP3) to reflect their merged workflow, and one additional dataset has been added (DAT_03_02_INRAE) following methodological refinement.

3.4.1. DATASETS

The Table 2 provides a comprehensive overview of datasets generated within the MOBILES project, highlighting their origin, format, description, and relevance to the project objectives. The datasets are project-generated data originating primarily from laboratory work and, reflecting diverse experimental activities across multiple work packages (WP) and tasks. These datasets aim to support the development of innovative biosensors and assess their environmental performance, as well as the development of a soil metagenomic database aligning with the project's key objectives: The data encompass a wide range of formats, including numeric values, textual descriptions, images, DNA and RNA sequences, and models.

Relevance of datasets produced within the project to its objectives:

- **Objective 1: Develop electronic biosensors for the detection of organic chemicals, antimicrobial-resistant (AMR) bacteria, and pathogens in water, soil, and air.**
 - DAT_01_NTUA
 - DAT_03_01_INRAE
 - DAT_03_02_INRAE
 - DAT_05_Eden
 - DAT_9_Ubx

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- DAT_11_UBE
- **Objective 2: Develop organism-based biosensors for monitoring organic and inorganic pollution in water and soil.**
 - DAT_02a_CNR-IRET
 - DAT_04_UR
 - DAT_08_1_ARO
 - DAT_08_2_ARO
 - DAT_08_3_ARO
 - DAT_08_4_ARO
 - DAT_08_5_ARO
 - DAT_08_6_ARO
 - DAT_08_7_ARO
 - DAT_10_CUT
 - DAT_12_Mat
 - DAT_13_TUC
- **Objective 3: Study the environmental performance of the developed organisms and devices.**
 - DAT_01_NTUA
 - DAT_02a_CNR-IRET
 - DAT_03_INRAE
 - DAT_08_8_ARO
 - DAT_08_9_ARO
 - DAT_11_UBE
 - DAT_12_Mat
 - DAT_13_TUC
- **Objective 4: Conduct metagenomics analysis of the microbiota in polluted areas to enable the identification of diverse functionalities across multiple gene clusters.**
 - DAT_02b_WP3
 - DAT_04_UR

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- **Objective 5: Perform safety tests (e.g., EFSA) to assess the impact of the developed organisms and devices on the natural environment.**
 - DAT_15_RICPA

3.4.2. OTHER RESEARCH OUTPUTS

The Table 3 provides a comprehensive overview of other research outputs (public deliverables of the project) generated within the MOBILES project. Public deliverables in the form of report will be published at the project website (www.mobiles-project.eu) once submitted and stored in the MOBILES community on Zenodo repository (<https://zenodo.org/communities/mobiles>) once approved by the Project Officer.

Overview in the Table 3 (*See Attachments*):

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4. MOBILES FAIR data (Findable-Accessible-Interoperable-Reusable)

4.1. FINDABLE DATA INCLUDING PROVISIONS FOR METADATA

The MOBILES project is founded on open collaboration and the systematic sharing of knowledge while adhering to the project's data policy, which emphasizes achieving maximum openness as early and widely as possible. All research data generated by the MOBILES project will be managed responsibly, in accordance with the FAIR principles and the requirements set out under Horizon Europe (as outlined in the Annotated Grant Agreement, notably in the Article 17).

To ensure the findability of MOBILES data, all datasets (including other research outputs) will be **assigned persistent identifiers**, preferably DOIs, via selected trusted repositories, preferably at Zenodo, where project has already set a MOBILES community, that will serve as a main point for the long-term storage of MOBILES project research datasets and other research outputs.

Comprehensive **metadata frameworks** will accompany relevant datasets except DAT_12_Mat and DAT_13_TUC. These opted-out in order to protect the know-how and potential application for patent protection. Other metadata will be made openly accessible under the public domain dedication **CC0 at trusted repository under open access**. The metadata will include details such as dataset descriptions, date of deposit, authorship, venue, and embargo status; Horizon Europe funding information, project name, acronym, and grant number; licensing terms; persistent identifiers for datasets, authors, and their organizations, where applicable. Furthermore, where possible, the metadata will link to related publications and research outputs will be made harvestable for AI tools.

MOBILES datasets will be categorized using common keywords, such as "biosensors," "organic chemicals," "antimicrobial resistance," and "environmental monitoring," (not exclusively) to facilitate searchability and cross-referencing.

Detailed overview on the Data findability including provisions for metadata is provided in the Table 4 (*See Attachments*)

4.2. ACCESSIBLE DATA

In the questionnaire, MOBILES partners were asked a set of questions related to the accessibility of datasets produced during the project. All datasets generated within the MOBILES project (open or restricted) will be deposited in Zenodo. This platform ensures that datasets are assigned a persistent identifier (Digital Object Identifier, DOI) and linked to related publications or other datasets.

For the UBE partner, they have decided to use an institutional repository alongside Zenodo. In the UBE repository (Cherry), each dataset version will be tagged and accompanied by appropriate metadata, with links established between different versions. The UBE team will also define a naming

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convention for metadata, datasets, and templates to ensure ease of discovery. This convention will consist of three mandatory parts:

- A prefix indicating whether the file is a dataset, metadata, or a template.
- A root composed of:
 - A short, meaningful name of the dataset/template.
 - The acronym or short name of the data provider partner(s) (PFASwin by default for templates).
- A suffix indicating the date of the last upload to the repository in YYYYMMDD format.

MOBILES team members are encouraged to use this platform to store datasets and archive project results. Datasets supporting scientific publications will be deposited at the time of publication, ensuring accessibility through free and standardized access protocols.

Similarly to UBE partner datasets, 2 other datasets will be stored in different repositories alongside Zenodo. These are:

- DAT_03_02_INRAE covering the mass spectrometry proteomics data, which have been deposited to the ProteomeXchange Consortium610 via the PRIDE partner repository with the dataset identifiers PXD06417 and PXD074845.
- DAT_02b_WP3 covering DNA sequences generated during the project (WP3), which will be deposited in the National Center for Biotechnology Information (NCBI) database, specifically in the Sequence Read Archive (SRA) section.

While the majority of datasets and other research outputs are aligned with the FAIR principles and are openly accessible, some datasets will have restricted access due to their potential for patent applications. These include:

- DAT_05_EDEN
- DAT_12_Mat
- DAT_13_TUC

Similarly, two project deliverables under WP1 with sensitive dissemination levels will have restricted access:

- D1.1 - Design, characterization, and optimization of aptamers, DNA/RNA probes, and enzymes for biosensors (INRAE).
- D1.3 - Microfluidic network for sensor integration (EDEN).

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Data will be retained and accessible for at least five years after the project's conclusion. Open datasets are expected to remain accessible long-term via Zenodo. Publicly accessible MOBILES datasets will be licensed under the Creative Commons Attribution International Public License (CC BY), while metadata will be licensed under the Creative Commons Public Domain Dedication (CC0). Ethical or legal issues related to data sharing will be carefully managed.

4.3. INTEROPERABLE DATA AND DATA RE-USE

The interoperability of datasets produced within the MOBILES project will be ensured through the use of open data formats, making them easier to validate, share, and reuse. Commonly used open formats include:

- CSV, PDF, DOCX, XLS, JPG, and PNG for general data representation.
- FASTQ, FASTQ.GZ, FQ, FQ.GZ AND POD5 for sequencing data.
- CAD for 2D/3D modelling.
- OPJ and OPJU for scientific graphing and data analysis.

Large majority of formats can be accessed by common tools such as MS Office, PDF viewer, web browser, default image browser. FASTQ and FASTA and other sequencing data formats can be easily viewed and processed using widely available software tools commonly used within the scientific community. However, CAD and OriginLab formats (OPJ and OPJU) are proprietary and require licensed tools such as CAD software or OriginLab. OPJ and OPJU files can also be accessed using Python libraries, though this may have limited functionality compared to OriginLab's software.

Summary in the Table 5 (*See Attachments*):

To facilitate reuse, the project team will provide detailed metadata and comprehensive documentation for all datasets. This includes:

- Comprehensive descriptions in linked peer-reviewed articles.
- Readme files or supplementary documentation for datasets that are not self-explanatory.

These measures will enhance data reproducibility and ensure compliance with the FAIR principles. Metadata and documentation will also aid in indexing and aggregation by data repositories and scientific aggregators. Where applicable, datasets will be accompanied by version tracking to document updates or revisions.

Summary in the Table 6 (*See Attachments*):

Internal data handling procedures will align with institutional practices of project partners to ensure smooth integration of data management processes. Any potential conflicts with the project's Data Management Plan (DMP) will be resolved through communication and resolution procedures managed by the project coordinator.

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5. CONCLUSION

The MOBILES project is a Horizon Europe- funded project, coordinated by the **National Technical University of Athens (NTUA)**, aiming to develop highly sensitive, portable, and low-cost biosensors for real-time environmental monitoring. These devices promise performance with equal or superior performance to existing techniques while being adaptable to onsite testing, enabling critical advancements in addressing pollutants such as pathogens, Chemicals of Emerging Concern (CECs), and Persistent Mobile Chemicals (PMCs). In parallel several soil microbiotas across Europe will be studied with metagenomic tools in order to identify gene clusters that are related to specific pollutants.

One of the main project management outputs is the comprehensive Data Management Plan (DMP), which adheres to the **EU Open Science policy and FAIR principles**. This living document, prepared initially by GRANT Garant (GG) during the project's early months, **defines 22 datasets and 21 other research outputs (public deliverables) and outlines the management** of these preliminary identified datasets. These datasets will be findable through persistent identifiers, detailed metadata, and accessible via trusted repositories mainly through **Zenodo**. Open access will be provided wherever feasible, under Creative Commons licenses, though certain datasets are safeguarded due to commercial exploitation interests.

The DMP also establishes mechanisms to ensure interoperability and reusability of project-generated data, leveraging commonly used and open formats, keywords, and metadata in desired format for long-term preservation. MOBILES' commitment to sustainability extends beyond the project's lifespan, with datasets guaranteed to be preserved for at least five years post-completion.

All datasets and outputs will be managed in accordance with the FAIR data principles, ensuring their findability, accessibility, interoperability, and reusability. This approach aims to contribute to the successful achievement of the MOBILES project goals and to boost the project impact, thereby enriching the European realm of science and innovation.

The next update on datasets produced within the MOBILES project lifespan are scheduled **M40** when an internal survey will be repeated and **submitted to the EC as a separate deliverable D6.4**.

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5. Attachments

Table 2: MOBILES project datasets - description

Table 3: Other research outputs

Table 4: Findability of data including provisions for metadata

Table 5: Interoperability of data

Table 6: Reusability of data

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6. List of Figures

n/a

7. List of Tables

Table 1: MOBILES WPs list

8. List of Abbreviations

Abbreviation	Abbreviation for
CC0	Creative Commons Public Domain Dedication
CC BY	Attribution International Public Licence
DMP	Data Management Plan
OA	Open Access

10. Project Consortium

www.ntua.gr/en/

www.cnr.it/en

www.inrae.fr/en

www.uniroma1.it/en/pagina-strutturale/home

www.eden-microfluidics.com/

<https://www.unavarra.es/home>

www.en.iung.pl/

www.agri.gov.it/en/home

www.u-bordeaux.fr/en

www.cut.ac.cy/?languageId=1

www.chem.bg.ac.rs/index-en.html

www.mat4nrg.de/

www.tu-clausthal.de/en/

www.grant-garant.cz

www.proakademia.eu/en/

